

methodology by example

Presentation by CNR, meeting 22/11/2022

- group of actors is too limited in the diagram, because there are a lot of actors not included, politicians, administrative, etc.
 - here we need to be anchored to the framework, but also to indicators that we want
 - nice graphical diagrams, visuals are nice
 - the like the visualisation that shows the change
 - who should make this representation?
 - probably too much detail
 - the diagram does not describe how much is happening beyond the farm
 - so the methodology appears to capture deep aspects of the system, but not sufficiently broad
- you designed the full process, and when I read through the proposal there are some overlapping activities. Is this process independent of other activities? The activities of LL need to be harmonised. Would this be integrated with WP4 and WP2?
- you introduce 3 different modelling schemes. Do we need to have the three? For what I see number 2 (goal) is interesting for modelling non-tangible benefits. So we will use it. Then the two other ones appear overlapping.
- who is making the modelling?
- this is a first idea proposed, and we need to enhance it, and we do not have to chose right now. We need to discuss this within WP2.